

THE EVOLUTION OF UZBEK NATIONAL COSTUMES

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Annotatsiya. O'qiydigan maqolangizda har doim o'zgarib turadigan kiyim uslublari va bu tez-tez o'zgarishlarning ba'zi sabablari, masalan, tarixiy voqealar, O'zbek milliy kiyimini va bugungi kunda qanday kiyinishimizni o'zgartirishga ta'sir qilgan voqealar haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Shuningdek, ushbu maqolada tikuvchilik texnikalari, to'qimalar, turli ranglarning ma'nosi va noyob naqshlar haqida ham ma'lumotlar taqdim etiladi. O'zbekistonda ko'plab an'anaviy tadbirlar va kiyim kiyish usullari mavjud. Odamlar to'liq yopiq kiyim kiygan, hatto yuzlari ham yashirilgan paytlar bo'lgan, shuningdek, juda ochiq kiyimlar, masalan, qisqa yubkalar, ochiq yelkalar kiygan paytlar ham bo'lgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek kiyimi, to'qima, tarix, evolyutsiya, madaniyat, an'anaviy.

Аннотация. Статья, которую вы прочитаете, содержит информацию о стилях одежды, которые меняются с течением времени, и о некоторых причинах этих частых изменений, таких как исторические события, оказавшие влияние на трансформацию узбекского национального костюма и на то, как мы одеваемся сегодня. Кроме того, в статье представлена информация о швейных техниках, тканях, а также о значении различных цветов и уникальных узоров. В Узбекистане существует множество традиционных мероприятий и способов ношения одежды. Бывали случаи, когда люди носили полностью закрытую одежду, даже лицо было скрыто, и были времена, когда одежда была очень откровенной, например, короткие юбки, открытые плечи.

Ключевые слова: узбекская одежда, ткань, история, эволюция, культура, традиции.

Abstract. The article you will read gives information about clothing styles that changes every time and some reasons for these frequent changes, such as historical events, that have influenced the transformation of Uzbek national attire and the way what we wear today. Additionally, this article provides information about sewing techniques, fabrics, and not only the meaning of various colors but also unique patterns. In Uzbekistan, there are many traditional events and ways of wearing clothes. There were situations when people wore completely closed clothes, even the face was hidden, and there were times when they dressed very revealingly, for example, short skirts, open shoulders.

Keywords: Uzbek clothing, cloth, history, evolution, culture, traditional.

Introduction. The evolution of Uzbek national costumes has been changed by many historical, cultural, and social influences. Some researchers have explored about how clothing reflects cultural identity and what causes changes in traditional outfits. The historical development of Uzbek national attire is closely connected to the country's geographic position. According to Istamova

(2024), the foundations of modern Uzbek clothing were shaped during the period when Central Asia was inhabited by Iranian nomadic tribes. Initially, clothing was simple, functional, and made from natural materials like animal skins and plant fibers (Davlatova, 2021).

The culture of dressing has faced significant transformations throughout history. “The purpose of wearing clothing is primarily to protect the body from environmental influences: heat and cold, wind, dust, sunlight, rain, etc” (Ochilova,2024). But over time, clothing has become more than just a way to keep warm or cool. It has evolved into a way for people to display and express themselves and their culture. Because of advances in technology, frequent changes of rulers with different cultures, and the exchange of goods through international trade, people changed their style of clothing. Due to the fact that Uzbekistan located in Central Asia, it has a rich cultural influence owing to its historical location along the Silk Road. Over the centuries, Uzbekistan has been influenced by various rulers and cultures, from Persian and Mongol to Russian and even Arab influences. Each of these cultures has contributed to the evolution of traditional Uzbek clothing, resulting in unique styles that reflect the country’s history and heritage. The changes in Uzbek national clothing are an interesting topic because they reflect important ideas about cultural identity, and adaptation. “National clothes reflect the ethnic history and culture of the people, their unique aesthetic views, tastes and traditions” (Yunusov,2022). In a rapidly changing world, examining how traditional dress evolves can help us understand a society's values and beliefs. Additionally, studying this topic helps preserve cultural heritage and shows how clothing can express culture. The purpose of this essay is to analyze the historical and cultural factors that have shaped Uzbek national dress over time. By examining these influences, I aim to highlight the significance of clothing as a form of cultural expression and identity.

“The modern vision of Uzbek clothes started constructing in the period when territories of current Central Asia was filled by Iranian nomadic and semi-nomadic tribes-Saks” (Istamova, 2024, p. 247). Initially, clothes were worn to protect the body from the heat or frost. They looked very simple, it can be called just piece of soft material without any seams. “Until the V century BC, only natural materials (animal skins, bark of trees, plant fibers) were used” (Davlatova, 2021, p. 35). As time went on, people began to innovate, transforming these basic materials into more functional decorative way. “In the historical-ethnographic literature, it was interpreted that the first step of the development of clothing was connected with the development of the technics of textile (net weaving and cloth weaving)” (Davlatova, 2021, p. 36). After, people began to wear them not only for protection but also to show their status by the unusual material they were covered with. From my research, it is clear that today, more people prefer to showcase beauty rather than simply covering or protecting their bodies

Figure 1.

Importance of clothing.

Why do people need clothes?

52 ответа

Note: The figure shows the result of why people usually wear clothes. This statistic is the opinion of 52 individuals. Looking at the result, it can be seen that people are more interested in showing their character and interest through the way they dress.

One of the main factors that influenced the appearing of new styles is militant change of rulers. For example at the beginning of 7th century, when ancient Uzbekistan was captured by the Arabs, they brought with them their traditions and religion. As a result, the way people dressed began to change. Everyone that time had to wear closed, dark clothes. Before the arrivals of the Arabs, locals wore bright and colorful cuttons that showcased their culture. However,with the introduction of Islamic beliefs,there happened dramatical changes. As Umarova mentioned in her work, “A critical impact on the recognition of color in outfit was religion as a social institution”(n.d.). Islam is a religion that does not endorse figurative pictures of living things. After many years, Russiaons made some news as well. “The wearing of closed clothes lasted until the 19th century, when Russia conquered Tashkent and Russian culture was introduced into Uzbek”(Istamova, 2024 p. 248).It strongly impacted on clothes, especially on openness of clothes. For instance, men started wearing shorter coats and lighter fabrics that were easier to move in, while women began to adopt dresses with different cuts and designs.Around the 20-70s of the 20 century European styled clothes also came into the traditional, national clothes.“We can see it in wearing national shirts with European trousers, and later, in wearing trousers with wide lower legs” (Davlatova, 2021, p. 36). Based on my research, I can say that European styles have been preserved in Uzbekistan to a large extent.

Figure 2.

Types of clothing style.

What style of clothind do you like best?

52 отбета

Note: As shown in figure 2, the most popular style is casual, chosen by 25% of people. National and minimalistic styles are equally preferred at 17.3%. Those who are not interested in style make up the smallest number of people.

In Uzbekistan, people have special occasional dresses. For example, brides always wear white color because it symbolize pure happiness while everyone in mourning wears dark colors like black and blue. Especially on holidays Uzbeks like to wear national dresses in order to preserve cultural uniqueness. One of them is “atlas” which is women’s common dress. This dress made of colorful silk that is decorated with unique pattern.Initially, all the patterns were made by hand, but over time, when new technologies appeared, they could be made using textile printers. Now with these advanced machines it is possible to not only draw patterns but also make 3D models and even make bead decoration. Moreover, we have an accessory called “do’ppi”. From

ancient times to the present day, the custom of wearing “duppi” still preserved. Especially new brides wear it 40 days which are variously decorated.

Figure 3.

Reason for wearing Uzbek national clothes.

How often do you wear national clothes?

52 ответа

Note: From the last figure, it can be seen how often people in Uzbekistan dress in national style and why they do it. Over half of the people wear traditional clothing only on holidays. Some people think that it is not their style, while others always dress that way. The good thing is that there is a small number of those who have not tried it.

In conclusion, Uzbek national clothes have long history. These national costumes can remind us of our past history and identity. From the beginning, style of clothing has undergone many changes, and thanks to new ideas of designers it may change even more, acquiring new highlights and of course preserving the past cultural significant.

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